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A Retrievable Ocean Petal Anchor for Marine Energy Devices

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Abstract

This research details the development, modeling, and testing of a retrievable anchor concept that is suitable for temporary or extended mooring of a marine energy device in sandy ocean floors. The Retrievable Ocean Petal Anchor (ROPA) device was envisioned as having two distinct configurations during installation and deployment. During installation, the device is largely cylindrical. The petals or flanks are folded down forming a cylinder around the central support tube. As the central support tube engages with the ocean floor, high pressure water is injected into the ocean floor, fluidizing the local region. This fluidized region has reduced resistance to the anchor embedment, allowing the device to be easily embedded at various depths. Once it reaches the prescribed depth, the petals are deployed by folding away from the central support tube. As with embedment, the deployment of the petals is facilitated by the reduced properties of the fluidized sand. The deployed petals significantly increase the surface area of the device engaging with the sediment, increasing the pullout load of the anchor. Once the injection of high-pressure water into the sediment is stopped, the soil quickly recovers its strength, creating a high strength mooring.

This concept has been investigated through a combination of geotechnical simulations, finite element analysis and physical prototyping. Geotechnical simulations in PLAXIS was used to determine the holding strength of the ROPA mooring. Initial simulations used a simplified axially symmetric model to determine the axial pullout strength, before moving to complete 3D model which was used to assess lateral loads and combined loading. Results from these simulations show an increased vertical pullout strength when compared to a comparably sized drag anchor. The ROPA device has another benefit over the drag anchor in that it needs a much shorter mooring line. These shorter mooring lines reduce the likelihood of entanglement and reduce the required spacing when deploying an array of devices.

The mechanical design of the ROPA was achieved through a combination of analytical calculations, finite element analysis, and physical testing. Analytical calculations and loading results from the geotechnical simulation served as the inputs for mechanical models that were used to size structural components. Once sized a physical prototype was constructed from a combination of off the shelf components and custom manufactured aluminum petals and brackets. The completed assembly has been tested to verify the fluidization assisted embedment process as well as the holding power of the device with deployed petals.

Keywords: Mooring, Anchors

1. Introduction and Modeling

With the advent of the 21st century technology, the generation of electrical power from multi sources including floating wind turbines, wave and current energy converters could serve as an economically viable source of

renewable energy for the mid-Atlantic region and contribute to the region's economic development. Whether self-buoyant such as floating wind turbines and wave energy converter devices or bottom fixed such as Gulf Stream current and tidal turbine, anchoring foundation systems will have to sustain multidirectional, time-dependent, loading from the energy devices as well vortices shedding from the mooring lines. Several anchoring points will be required and when deployed on experimental basis (as for example will be the case during the "Waves to Water prize 2022," the ability to install and retrieve these anchoring points will provide a great flexibility in responding to the need of the offshore renewable energy industry as well as provide flexibility to restore site to once a project is completed.

Screw piles are currently one potential alternative to serve as a retrievable anchor. The first documented use of screw piles was in the 19th century England for supporting lighthouses [1]. The installation of screw piles however requires the use of specialized rig for the application of torque accompanied by downward pressure [2]. In addition, voids between each helix are created during installation which necessitate the application of grouts to fill out these voids. As such the installation and retrieval of screw piles in ocean environment becomes rather challenging.

An alternative concept that is being proposed is a Retrievable Ocean Petal Anchor (ROPA) as shown in Figure 1a below. The ROPA device consists of multiple flanks or 'petals' which form a cylinder for insertion into the soil. Once embedded to the desired depth, the petals are flared out to increase the pullout strength of the device. Insertion of the device and flaring of the petals are facilitated by the introduction of high pressure water through the central nozzle. This water fluidize the sandy soil, reducing its resistance to deployment. Once the device is embedded to the desired depth and the petals are deployed, the flow of water is stopped and the surrounding soil returns to it prior strength (~95% after 24 hours).

A simplified version of the geometry is shown in Figure 1b, which was used to analyze the anchor strength based on the pullout load (P), embedded depth (H), and the angle of petal deployment (θ). The angle of the pullout load was also varied from purely vertical to a combined vertical and lateral loaded. The geo-technical finite element analyses was performed in PLAXIS as shown in Figure 1c. Initial results indicate that the ROPA device would have superior vertical pullout resistance to commonly used drag anchors of comparable size.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of the ROPA device (a) simplified analytical model (b) results of geotechnical analysis of the design

2. Results and Discussion

To verify the operation of the ROPA device, a sub-scale prototype was constructed based on the mechanical design shown in Figure 2a below. A central threaded pipe shown in green serves as both a central guide for petal slide carriages and the source of the high pressure water to fluidize the surrounding soil. The nozzle at the end is a commercial off the shelf threaded cap which has been modified to introduce axial and radial holes to allow for the flow of water. As the threaded nozzle is easily replaced, it allows for multiple hole configurations to be readily tested to experimentally determine which hole pattern is most effective at fluidizing the local soil.

For this early stage prototype, commercially available aluminum pipe and CNC machined aluminum petals and hardware were used as shown in Figure 2b. For actual ocean deployments marine grade materials would be employed. Preliminary testing of the sub-scale prototype confirmed the ability of the ROPA device to fluidize the local soil through water jetting and to increase the pullout strength of the device when the petals are deployed as show in Figure 2c. This confirmation of the fluidization and deployment processes coupled with the simulation results indicating improved vertical pullout capacity supports the potential of the ROPA device as a retrievable anchor with improved vertical strength compared to drag anchors and easier deployment than a screw anchor.

Figure 2: Mechanical design of the ROPA device (a) sub-scale ROPA device with petals collapsed (b) sub-scale ROPA device with the petals deployed (c)

3. Acknowledgments

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References

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